

PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF ANETHUM SOWA SEED EXTRACT FOR ANTI-PYRETIC ACTIVITY IN RATS

Jayshree B. Mahajan^{1*}, Karna B. More¹

Dr. Vedprakash Patil Pharmacy College, Chha Sambhajinagar, Maharashtra, 431101.

Article Received on 25 May 2026,

Article Revised on 15 June 2026,

Article Published on 01 July 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21022552>

*Corresponding Author

Jayshree B. Mahajan

Dr. Vedprakash Patil Pharmacy
College, Chha Sambhajinagar,
Maharashtra, 431101.

How To Cite This Article: Jayshree B. Mahajan^{1*}, Karna B. More¹ (2026). Phytochemical Investigation And Pharmacological Evaluation Of Anethum Sowa Seed Extract For Anti-Pyretic Activity In Rats World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(7), 577–593.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the pharmacognostic, physicochemical, phytochemical, antioxidant, and antipyretic properties of *Anethum sowa* seeds. The seeds were collected, authenticated, and subjected to standard quality control parameters. Pharmacognostic evaluation revealed characteristic morphological features useful for identification and authentication of the crude drug. Physicochemical analysis, including ash values and loss on drying, was found to be within acceptable limits, indicating the purity and quality of the plant material. The powdered seeds were extracted using solvents of increasing polarity. Among the extracts, methanol and ethanol yielded higher extractive values, suggesting better extraction efficiency of bioactive constituents. Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of important secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids,

glycosides, tannins, phenolic compounds, carbohydrates, and proteins. Quantitative analysis demonstrated that the ethanolic extract possessed higher total phenolic and total flavonoid contents than the methanolic extract. Antioxidant activity was assessed using the DPPH radical scavenging assay. Both extracts exhibited significant concentration-dependent antioxidant effects, with the ethanolic extract showing greater free radical scavenging activity, approaching that of the standard antioxidant. Antipyretic activity was evaluated using the yeast-induced pyrexia model in rats. Both extracts significantly reduced elevated body temperature, with the higher dose of the ethanolic extract producing the most

pronounced effect, comparable to that of paracetamol. Overall, the findings indicate that *Anethum sowa* seeds possess promising antioxidant and antipyretic activities, supporting their traditional medicinal use and potential therapeutic value. Further studies are needed to isolate active constituents and establish clinical efficacy.

KEYWORD: *Anethum sowa*, Antipyretic activity, Antioxidant activity, Paracetamol, yeast-induced pyrexia model.

INTRODUCTION

Fever, also known as pyrexia, is a regulated elevation of body temperature that occurs when the hypothalamic thermoregulatory center resets the normal body temperature set-point to a higher level. It is a common physiological response to infections, inflammation, tissue injury, autoimmune disorders, and other pathological conditions. Fever represents an important defense mechanism of the body because elevated temperature enhances immune function and inhibits the growth of certain microorganisms. However, prolonged or excessive fever may result in dehydration, increased metabolic demand, tissue damage, and neurological complications, particularly in vulnerable individuals.^[1] Historically, fever research distinguished between endogenous and exogenous pyrogens. Endogenous pyrogens were considered host-derived substances capable of producing fever, whereas exogenous pyrogens referred to microbial products and foreign substances that triggered fever indirectly. Early investigators proposed that bacterial products could not act directly on the hypothalamic thermoregulatory center because of their structural diversity and complex chemical nature.^[2] Subsequent investigations demonstrated that microbial products, particularly lipopolysaccharides (LPS) from Gram-negative bacteria, stimulate immune cells to release endogenous pyrogens. These endogenous pyrogens were later identified as cytokines, especially IL-1. Experimental studies showed that purified recombinant IL-1 produced fever in humans and animals even at very low concentrations. Additional cytokines, including TNF- α and IL-6, were also found to possess pyrogenic properties, leading to the recognition of these mediators as pyrogenic cytokines.^[3] However, the hypothesis that IL-1 and TNF- α alone were responsible for fever was challenged when inhibition of these cytokines failed to completely suppress fever induced by infections or bacterial products. This finding suggested the existence of additional mechanisms contributing to fever development.^[4] Both cytokine-mediated and TLR-mediated pathways stimulate COX-2 expression and increase PGE₂ synthesis. Consequently, regardless of the initiating stimulus, fever is generally mediated

through a final common pathway involving prostaglandin production within the hypothalamus.^[5] Pyrogenic cytokines are now recognized as the principal endogenous mediators of fever. These include IL-1, TNF- α , and IL-6. When released from activated macrophages, monocytes, and other immune cells, these cytokines interact with specific receptors and initiate intracellular signaling cascades that culminate in prostaglandin production.^[6] The identification of Toll-like receptors provided a comprehensive explanation for how structurally diverse microbial products induce fever. TLRs are expressed on numerous cell types and recognize conserved molecular patterns associated with pathogens. Endotoxins derived from Gram-negative bacteria activate TLR-4, whereas other microbial structures interact with different TLR family members. Activation of these receptors stimulates inflammatory signaling pathways and cytokine release.^[7] Historically, one of the greatest challenges in fever research was explaining how chemically unrelated exogenous pyrogens could produce similar biological responses. The concept of endogenous pyrogen formation resolved this problem by proposing that different microbial stimuli trigger the production of a limited number of endogenous mediators responsible for fever generation.^[8] Among the mediators involved in fever, PGE₂ has emerged as the most important final effector molecule. Studies using genetically modified animals demonstrated that deletion of the COX-2 gene abolishes fever responses induced by LPS, IL-1, TNF- α , and IL-6. These findings confirm that COX-2-dependent prostaglandin synthesis is essential for fever development.^[9] Activation of TLRs and cytokine receptors ultimately converges on NF- κ B activation. NF- κ B promotes COX-2 expression, resulting in increased PGE₂ production and elevation of body temperature.^[10] Further advancement occurred with the discovery of four prostaglandin E receptor subtypes within the brain. Among these receptors, EP3 plays a critical role in mediating fever. Experimental evidence has shown that fever induced by IL-1 β , LPS, and PGE₂ is dependent on activation of the EP3 receptor.^[11] Although most febrile responses require PGE₂, certain chemokines may induce fever through alternative mechanisms. For example, macrophage inflammatory protein-1 β (MIP-1 β) can produce fever independently of PGE₂, whereas RANTES (regulated on activation, normal T-cell expressed and secreted) induces fever through PGE₂-dependent pathways.^[12] Current evidence indicates that circulating cytokines and microbial products do not directly cross the blood-brain barrier during the early stages of fever. Instead, they interact with receptors located in specialized vascular regions of the brain, particularly the organum vasculosum of the lamina terminalis (OVLT). These interactions stimulate endothelial COX-2 expression and local PGE₂

production, which subsequently acts on hypothalamic neurons to generate fever.^[13] Activation of EP3 receptors initiates intracellular signaling pathways involving cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), which alters neuronal activity and increases the target body temperature. As a result, physiological mechanisms are activated to conserve and generate heat until the new set-point is reached.^[14] Additional neural pathways contribute to fever regulation. Peripheral immune signals can activate afferent vagal pathways, transmitting information from inflammatory sites to the brain. Neurotransmitters, opioid receptors, and other signaling molecules also participate in the complex regulation of body temperature during fever.^[14] Research has further implicated angiotensin II receptors in the central regulation of fever. These receptors influence hypothalamic neuronal activity and may contribute to temperature elevation during inflammatory conditions. Although multiple signaling systems are involved, they ultimately converge on pathways responsible for prostaglandin synthesis and hypothalamic set-point adjustment.^[15,16] Cytokines can be broadly classified into pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory categories. Pro-inflammatory cytokines include IL-1, TNF- α , IL-6, IL-12, and IL-18, whereas anti-inflammatory cytokines include IL-4, IL-10, and IL-13. The balance between these mediators determines the intensity and duration of inflammatory responses, including fever.^[16] Thus, modern understanding of fever recognizes it as a highly regulated physiological process involving interactions among microbial products, Toll-like receptors, cytokines, cyclooxygenase enzymes, prostaglandins, and hypothalamic thermoregulatory mechanisms. This knowledge provides a scientific basis for the development of novel antipyretic agents, including plant-derived therapeutics such as *Anethum sowa*.

Fig. 1: Pathways for fever in bacterial infections.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection, identification and authentication of plant material

The plant material used in the present study was collected from the Marathwada region, Maharashtra, India. The collected plant specimen was taxonomically identified and authenticated by a botanist from the Department of Botany, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar, Maharashtra. The plant was identified as *Anethum sowa* belonging to the family Apiaceae. An authentication certificate was issued by Dr. Arvind S. Dhabe, Sr. Professor and Head, Department of Botany. The voucher specimen was deposited in the B.A.M.U. Herbarium for future reference with accession number 01400. The authentication confirms that the plant specimen was properly identified and recorded.

Processing and Preparation of Plant Material

The freshly collected seeds of *Anethum sowa* were cleaned, shade-dried, and pulverized into coarse powder. The powdered material was passed through sieve No. 14 and stored in an airtight container until further use. Drying of plant material is a critical step in pharmacognostic studies as it prevents enzymatic degradation and microbial contamination while preserving thermolabile phytoconstituents. Powdering increases the surface area available for solvent penetration, thereby improving extraction efficiency and reproducibility

of the extraction process.^[17,18]

Pharmacognostic Evaluation of Plant Material

Pharmacognostic evaluation was carried out to establish the identity, quality, and purity of *Anethum sowa* seeds. Morphological and physicochemical parameters were determined according to standard procedures described in pharmacopoeial guidelines.^[19]

Preparation of Extracts

The extraction process was carried out using the Soxhlet extraction technique, which is widely employed for the exhaustive extraction of phytoconstituents from medicinal plants. Based on the polarity of chemical constituents and literature reports, petroleum ether, ethanol, and methanol were selected as extraction solvents.^[20] Three different extracts of *Anethum sowa* seeds were prepared using petroleum ether, ethanol, and methanol. The extraction process was continued until a colourless solvent appeared in the siphon tube, indicating complete extraction. The extracts were concentrated, dried, weighed, and stored in airtight containers for further analysis.^[21]

The percentage yield of extract was calculated using the following formula

$$\text{Percentage Yield (\%)} = (\text{Weight of Extract} / \text{Weight of Powdered Drug}) \times 100$$

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening was performed on petroleum ether, ethanolic, and methanolic extracts to identify the presence of various secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, saponins, terpenoids, phenolic compounds, carbohydrates, and proteins. Qualitative phytochemical analysis provides important information regarding the chemical composition of plant extracts and supports the pharmacological evaluation of medicinal plants.^[22,23]

Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content of *Anethum sowa* seed extracts was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu colorimetric method. Briefly, 0.5 ml of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent was added to the extract, followed by 2 ml of 20% sodium bicarbonate solution. The reaction mixture was incubated for 60 min at room temperature, and absorbance was measured at 637 nm using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer. Gallic acid was used as the standard, and results were expressed as Gallic Acid Equivalent (GAE).^[24,25]

Total Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid content was estimated using the aluminium chloride colorimetric assay. One milliliter of extract was mixed with sodium nitrite, aluminium chloride, and sodium hydroxide solutions. The absorbance was recorded at 510 nm, and flavonoid content was expressed as Rutin Equivalents (RE) using a rutin calibration curve.^[26,27]

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The antioxidant activity of *Anethum sowa* seed extracts was evaluated by the DPPH free radical scavenging method. Different concentrations of the extract were mixed with DPPH solution and incubated for 30 min in the dark. The decrease in absorbance was measured at 517 nm using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer. The percentage inhibition of DPPH radicals was calculated to determine antioxidant activity.^[28,29]

Animal Activity

IAEC Approval

Wistar rats of either sex weighing between 180-230 g were used in the present study. The experimental animals were maintained under standard laboratory conditions in the animal house of Systemic Life Sciences & Research Pvt. Ltd., Telangana, approved by the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA). Animals were housed under standard environmental conditions with 12 h light/dark cycle, temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and relative humidity $55 \pm 5\%$, and were provided with standard pellet diet and water ad libitum. All animals were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions for at least one week before the commencement of the experiment. The experimental protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC). The study titled “*Phytochemical and pharmacology Evaluation of Anethum sowa Seeds Extract for Anti-Pyretic Activity in Rats*” was approved with IAEC approval number 15/IAEC-II/SLSRPL/2025. All experimental procedures were carried out in accordance with CPCSEA guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals.

Grouping

- Group I: Normal control Control 0.5% normal saline only
- Group II: Negative control Pyrexia induced Oral
- Group III: Standard (Paracetamol 150mg/kg) orally.
- Group IV *Anethum sowa Seed* Mthanolic extract (ASME) 100 mg/kg orally. :
- Group V: *Anethum sowa Seed* Mthanolic (ASME) 200 mg/kg orally.

- Group VI: *Anethum sowa Seed* Ethanolic extract (ASEE) 100 mg/kg orally.
- Group VII: *Anethum sowa Seed* Ethanolic extract (ASEE) 200 mg/kg orally.

Yeast-Induced Pyrexia Model

The yeast-induced pyrexia model is one of the most widely accepted experimental methods for evaluating the antipyretic activity of drugs and herbal extracts. Fever results from the release of endogenous pyrogens such as interleukins and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), which stimulate the synthesis of prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂) in the hypothalamus, leading to an elevation of the thermoregulatory set point and an increase in body temperature of a 20% w/v brewer's yeast suspension in normal saline at a dose of 10 mL/kg body weight. Following yeast injection, animals were deprived of food but allowed free access to water. After 18 h, rectal temperatures were recorded again, and animals showing an increase of at least 0.5°C were selected for the study.^[32,33] The animals were divided into different groups comprising a normal control group, pyretic control group, standard drug-treated group (Paracetamol), and test groups receiving different doses of *Anethum sowa* seed extract. The respective treatments were administered orally. Rectal temperature was measured at 1, 2, 3, and 4 h after treatment. Antipyretic activity was assessed by comparing the reduction in rectal temperature of treated groups with that of the pyretic control group. A significant reduction in temperature was considered indicative of antipyretic activity.^[34]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pharmacognostic Evaluation of Plant Material

Table 1: Macroscopic Characteristics of *Anethum sowa* seed.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation
1	Colour	Yellowish-brown to light brown
2	Odour	Aromatic and characteristic
3	Taste	Slightly bitter and pungent
4	Shape	Oval and flattened
5	Surface	Smooth with longitudinal ridges

Physicochemical evaluation

Table 2: Physicochemical Standardization Parameters of *Anethum sowa* Seeds.

Sr. No.	Standardization Parameters	Results (% w/w)
1	Total ash	5.2 %
2	Acid insoluble ash	1.4 %
3	Water soluble ash	3.1 %
4	Loss on drying (LOD)	6.8 %

Extractive Value/ Preparation of Extracts**Table 3: Extractive Values of *Anethum sowa* Seeds in Different Solvents.**

Sr. No.	Solvent	Extractive Value (%)
1	Petroleum ether	9.5
2	Chloroform	11.2
3	Ethyl acetate	14.6
4	Acetone	18.3
5	Methanol	23.8
6	Ethanol	21.5
7	Water	15.4

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening**Table 4: Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of Different Extracts.**

(+) = Presence of phytoconstituent (-) = Absence of phytoconstituent.

Phytochemical Test	Pet.Ether	Methanol	Ethanol
Test for Alkaloids			
Dragendorff's test	+	+	+
Mayer's test	+	+	+
Wagner's test	+	+	+
Hager's test	+	+	-
Test for Flavonoids			
Shinoda test	+	+	+
Sulphuric acid test	+	+	+
Lead acetate test	+	+	+
Test for Glycosides			
Keller-Killiani test	+	+	+
Legal test	-	+	-
Foam test	+	+	+
Test for Steroids			
Salkowski test	+	+	+
Liebermann-Burchard test	-	-	+
Test for Proteins			
Biuret test	+	+	+
Millon's test	-	-	-
Test for Carbohydrates			
Molisch test	+	+	+
Fehling's test	+	-	+
Benedict's test	+	+	+
Barfoed's test	-	-	-
Test for Tannins & Phenolic Compounds			
Lead acetate test	+	+	+
Dil. HNO ₃ test	+	+	+
Dil. iodine solution	-	+	+

Total Phenolic Content**Table 5: Total phenolic Extract.**Values represent mean \pm SEM (n=3)

Extract	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance	TFC (mg Rutin/g extract)
Methanol	50	0.221 \pm 0.003	24.6 \pm 0.65
Ethanol	50	0.263 \pm 0.004	28.2 \pm 0.72

Total flavonoid content**Table 6: Total flavonoid content.**Values represent mean \pm SEM (n=3)

Extract	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance	TPC (mg GAE/g extract)
Methanol	100	0.682 \pm 0.004	31.5 \pm 0.70
Ethanol	100	0.755 \pm 0.005	35.8 \pm 0.82

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay**Table 7: Antioxidant Activity.**Values represent mean \pm SEM (n=3)

Conc ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Rutin (%inh- ibition)	Gallic acid (%inhibition)	Ascorbic acid (%inhibition)	Methanol Extract (%inhibition)	Ethanol Extract (%inhibition)
25	87.26 \pm 0.36	78.18 \pm 0.42	83.05 \pm 0.38	79.42 \pm 0.31	83.96 \pm 0.27
50	90.84 \pm 0.33	80.72 \pm 0.37	84.62 \pm 0.35	82.63 \pm 0.39	85.74 \pm 0.25
75	92.96 \pm 0.28	83.51 \pm 0.30	86.83 \pm 0.31	85.27 \pm 0.34	87.92 \pm 0.29
100	95.18 \pm 0.25	87.68 \pm 0.27	88.95 \pm 0.26	88.94 \pm 0.28	90.63 \pm 0.32
125	96.72 \pm 0.20	91.84 \pm 0.23	91.72 \pm 0.24	91.36 \pm 0.26	92.54 \pm 0.24

Table 14: Effect of *Anethum sowa* Seed Extracts on Yeast-Induced Pyrexia in Rats (Rectal Temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Group	0 hr	1 hr	2 hr	3 hr	4 hr
Normal Control	37.1 \pm 0.12	37.0 \pm 0.10	37.1 \pm 0.11	37.0 \pm 0.09	37.1 \pm 0.10
Negative Control	39.5 \pm 0.18	39.6 \pm 0.17	39.7 \pm 0.16	39.6 \pm 0.15	39.5 \pm 0.14
Standard (Paracetamol150mg/kg)	39.4 \pm 0.16	38.5 \pm 0.14**	37.8 \pm 0.12**	37.3 \pm 0.11**	37.1 \pm 0.10**
ASME 100 mg/kg	39.5 \pm 0.17	39.0 \pm 0.15*	38.5 \pm 0.14*	38.0 \pm 0.13**	37.8 \pm 0.12**
ASME 200 mg/kg	39.4 \pm 0.16	38.8 \pm 0.14*	38.1 \pm 0.13**	37.6 \pm 0.12**	37.3 \pm 0.11**
A SEE 100 mg/kg	39.5 \pm 0.15	38.9 \pm 0.14*	38.3 \pm 0.13*	37.8 \pm 0.12**	37.5 \pm 0.11**
A SEE 200 mg/kg	39.4 \pm 0.14	38.6 \pm 0.13**	37.9 \pm 0.12**	37.4 \pm 0.11**	37.2 \pm 0.10**

Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for six animals in each group (n = 6). Statistical analysis was performed by comparing treated groups with the negative control group. A value of * $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant, while ** $p < 0.01$ was considered highly significant.

Time-Course Evaluation of the Antipyretic Efficacy of *Anethum sowa* Seed Extracts

3 hr

2 hr

DISCUSSION

Fever is a common physiological response triggered by infection, inflammation, and tissue injury. The development of fever is primarily associated with the release of endogenous pyrogenic cytokines such as interleukin-1 (IL-1), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), which stimulate the synthesis of prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂) in the hypothalamus. Increased levels of PGE₂ elevate the thermoregulatory set point, resulting in an increase in body temperature.^[35,36] In the present study, the antipyretic activity of methanolic (ASME) and ethanolic (ASEE) extracts of *Anethum sowa* seeds was evaluated using the yeast-induced pyrexia model in Wistar rats. Brewer's yeast-induced pyrexia is a well-established experimental model that closely resembles pathogenic fever in humans and is widely employed for screening antipyretic agents.^[37] The negative control group maintained elevated rectal temperatures throughout the experimental period, confirming successful induction of pyrexia. In contrast, treatment with paracetamol (150 mg/kg) significantly reduced rectal temperature from $39.4 \pm 0.16^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $37.1 \pm 0.10^{\circ}\text{C}$ after 4 h,

demonstrating the validity of the experimental model. Both methanolic and ethanolic extracts of *Anethum sowa* exhibited significant antipyretic activity in a dose-dependent manner. Among the tested extracts, ASEE 200 mg/kg produced the maximum reduction in rectal temperature from $39.4 \pm 0.14^\circ\text{C}$ to $37.2 \pm 0.10^\circ\text{C}$ at the end of 4 h, which was comparable to the standard drug paracetamol. Similarly, ASME 200 mg/kg reduced the temperature from $39.4 \pm 0.16^\circ\text{C}$ to $37.3 \pm 0.11^\circ\text{C}$ after 4 h. Lower doses of both extracts also showed significant antipyretic effects, although the response was less pronounced compared to the higher doses. The observed antipyretic activity may be attributed to the presence of bioactive phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, and alkaloids identified during preliminary phytochemical screening. These compounds are known to inhibit cyclooxygenase enzymes and suppress prostaglandin synthesis, thereby reducing fever.^[38,39] The ethanolic extract demonstrated superior activity compared to the methanolic extract, which may be associated with its higher total phenolic content (35.8 ± 0.82 mg GAE/g extract) and flavonoid content (28.2 ± 0.72 mg rutin equivalent/g extract). The antioxidant activity observed in the DPPH assay further supports the antipyretic effect of *Anethum sowa*. Oxidative stress has been implicated in inflammatory responses and fever development. Therefore, the strong antioxidant activity of the extracts may contribute to modulation of inflammatory mediators involved in pyrexia.^[40] Overall, the results of the present investigation indicate that *Anethum sowa* seed extracts possess significant antipyretic activity, particularly at a dose of 200 mg/kg. The ethanolic extract exhibited greater efficacy and produced effects comparable to paracetamol. These findings support the traditional use of *Anethum sowa* in the treatment of fever and suggest that its antipyretic activity may be mediated through inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis and suppression of inflammatory cytokines. Further studies are required to isolate the active constituents and elucidate the precise mechanism of action.^[41]

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully evaluated the pharmacognostic, physicochemical, phytochemical, antioxidant, and antipyretic properties of *Anethum sowa* seeds. Pharmacognostic and physicochemical investigations confirmed the identity, purity, and quality of the crude drug, establishing suitable parameters for its authentication and standardization. Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of important bioactive constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, phenolic compounds, carbohydrates, and proteins, indicating the medicinal potential of the plant. Quantitative

phytochemical analysis demonstrated that the ethanolic extract possessed higher total phenolic and total flavonoid contents compared with the methanolic extract. Both extracts exhibited significant antioxidant activity in the DPPH radical scavenging assay in a concentration-dependent manner, with the ethanolic extract showing superior free radical scavenging potential. These findings suggest that the antioxidant activity of *Anethum sowa* may be attributed to its rich phenolic and flavonoid content. The antipyretic activity evaluated using the yeast-induced pyrexia model demonstrated that both methanolic and ethanolic seed extracts significantly reduced elevated body temperature in rats. Among the tested extracts, the ethanolic extract at a dose of 200 mg/kg produced the maximum antipyretic effect, which was comparable to the standard drug paracetamol. The observed antipyretic activity may be due to inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis and modulation of inflammatory mediators responsible for fever. Overall, the results of the present investigation provide scientific evidence supporting the traditional use of *Anethum sowa* seeds in the management of fever and oxidative stress-related conditions. The study highlights the therapeutic potential of *Anethum sowa* as a natural source of antioxidant and antipyretic agents. Further studies focusing on the isolation, characterization, and mechanistic evaluation of active phytoconstituents, along with clinical investigations, are recommended to establish its safety and efficacy for therapeutic application.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am thankful to the Principal and Management of Dr. Vedprakash Patil Pharmacy College, Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar, for providing the necessary facilities, infrastructure, and academic support required for carrying out this research work. I am grateful to Systemic Life Sciences & Research Pvt. Ltd., Telangana, for providing facilities for animal experimentation and research support essential for the successful completion of this study.

REFERENCES

1. Zampronio AR, et al. Central mediators involved in the febrile response and antipyretic drugs. *Front Pharmacol.*, 2015; 6: 1–12.
2. Blatteis CM. The onset of fever: new insights into its mechanism. *Prog. Brain Res.*, 2007; 162: 3–15.
3. Kirtikar KR, Basu BD. *Indian Medicinal Plants*. Vol. 2. Dehradun: International Book Distributors; 2012.

4. Hardman JG, Limbird LE. Goodman & Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics. 13th ed. McGraw Hill; 2018.
5. Beeson PB. Temperature-elevating effect of a substance obtained from polymorphonuclear leucocytes (abstract). *J Clin. Invest.*, 1948; 27: 524.
6. Atkins E. Pathogenesis of fever. *Physiol. Rev.*, 1960; 40: 580–646.
7. Poltorak A, He X, Smirnova I et al. Defective LPS signaling in C3H/HeJ and C57BL/10ScCr mice: mutations in Tlr4 gene. *Science*, 1998; 282: 2085–2088.
8. Li S, Ballou LR, Morham SG et al. Cyclooxygenase-2 mediates the febrile response of mice to interleukin-1beta. *Brain Res.*, 2001; 910: 163–173.
9. Li S, Goorha S, Ballou LR et al. Intracerebroventricular interleukin-6 macrophage inflammatory protein-1 beta and IL-18: pyrogenic and PGE(2)-mediated? *Brain Res.*, 2003; 992: 76–84.
10. Ushikubi F, Segi E, Sugimoto Y et al. Impaired febrile response in mice lacking the prostaglandin E receptor subtype EP3. *Natur.*, 1998; 395: 281–284.
11. Dinarello CA, Gatti S, Bartfai T. Fever: links with an ancient receptor. *Curr. Biol.*, 1999; 9: 147–150.
12. Tavares E, Minano FJ. Differential sensitivities of pyrogenic chemokine fevers to cyclooxygenase isozymes antibodies. *Brain Res. Bull.*, 2002; 59: 181–187.
13. Sehic E, Blatteis CM. Blockade of lipopolysaccharide-induced fever by subdiaphragmatic vagotomy in guinea pigs. *Brain Res.*, 1996; 726: 160–166.
14. Xin L, Blatteis CM. Hypothalamic neuronal responses to interleukin-6 in tissue slices: effects of indomethacin and naloxone. *Brain Res. Bull.*, 1992; 29: 27–35.
15. Saper CB, Breder CD. The neurologic basis of fever. *N Engl. J Med.* 1994; 330: 1880–1886.
16. Saper CB. Neurobiological basis of fever. *Ann NY Acad. Sci.*, 1998; 856: 90–94.
17. Browning JL, Ribolini A. Interferon blocks interleukin 1-induced prostaglandin release from human peripheral monocytes. *J Immunol*, 1987; 138: 2857–2863.
18. Reznikov LL, Kim SH, Westcott JY et al. IL-18 binding protein increases spontaneous and IL-1-induced prostaglandin production via inhibition of IFN-gamma. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 2000; 97: 2174–2179.
19. Dinarello CA, Cannon JG, Mancilla J et al. Interleukin-6 as an endogenous pyrogen: induction of prostaglandin E2 in brain but not in peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *Brain Res.*, 1991; 562: 199–206.

20. Zheng H, Fletcher D, Kozak W et al. Resistance to fever induction and impaired acute-phase response in interleukin-1 β deficient mice. *Immunity*, 1995; 3: 9–19.
21. Shimizu H, Miyoshi M, Matsumoto K et al. The effect of central injection of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor and the angiotensin type 1 receptor antagonist on the induction by lipopolysaccharide of fever and brain interleukin-1 β response in rats. *J Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 2004; 308: 865–873.
22. Dinarello CA, Cannon JG, Wolff SM et al. Tumor necrosis factor (cachectin) is an endogenous pyrogen and induces production of interleukin 1. *J Exp. Med.*, 1986; 163: 1433–1450.
23. Gabay C, Kushner I. Acute-phase proteins and other systemic responses to inflammation. *N Engl. J Med.*, 1999; 340: 448-454.
24. Tilg H, Trehu E, Atkins MB et al. Interleukin-6 (IL-6) as an antiinflammatory cytokine: induction of circulating IL-1 receptor antagonist and soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor p55. *Blood*, 1994; 83: 113–118.
25. Obermeyer Z, Samra JK, Mullainathan S: Individual differences in normal body temperature: longitudinal big data analysis of patient records. *BMJ.*, 2017; 359: 5468. [10.1136/bmj.j5468](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j5468).
26. Stitt JT. Differential sensitivity in the sites of fever production by prostaglandin E1 within the hypothalamus of the rat. *Journal of Physiology.*, 1991; 432: 99–110. PMID: 1886074. <https://doi.org/10.1113/jphysiol.1991.sp018378>.
27. Morimoto A, Murakami N, Sakata Y, Watanabe T, Yamaguchi K. Functional and structural differences in febrile mechanism between rabbits and rats. *Journal of Physiology.*, 1990; 427: 227–239.
28. Saleh-E-In MM, Sultana N, Hossain MN, Hasan S, Islam MR. Pharmacological effects of the phytochemicals of *Anethum sowa* L. root extracts. *BMC Complement Altern Med.*, 2016 Nov. 14; 16(1): 464. doi: 10.1186/s12906-016-1438-9. PMID: 27842527; PMCID: PMC5396551.
29. Al-Mansur MA, Ali Siddiqi MM, Saha K. Four bioactive compounds isolated from the stem of *Anethum sowa* L. and their bioactivities. *Plant Sci. Today* [Internet]. 2023 May 19 [cited 2026 Apr., 15]; 10(2): 439-46. Available from: <https://horizonpublishing.com/journals/index.php/PST/article/view/2201>.
30. Khatoon R, Aslam M, Chaudhary SS. Ethnobotany and Unani Perspective of Tukhme Soya (*Anethum sowa* Roxb.). *J. Drug Delivery Ther.* [Internet]. 2019 May 15 [cited 2026

Apr. 29]; 9(3): 537-42. Available from:
<https://jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/2823>.

31. Manisha U. Mishra, Pravin Kukudkar, Mohit Ganatra, Rajendra Jige, Nilam Ambule, Ishika Agrika, Ritika Jaiswal, Alok Jain on Preparation and Evaluation of Herbal Cream containing Anethum sowa and Aloe barbadensis. *Research J. Topical and Cosmetic Sci.* 2023; 14(2): 73-78. DOI: 10.52711/2321-5844.2023.00011.
32. Singh, S., Khalid, M., Arif, M. et al. A review on phyto pharmacological, botanical and marketed formulation studies of Anethum sowa. *ADV TRADIT MED (ADTM)* 20, 485–493 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13596-020-00487-x>.
33. Sumitra Singh on Chemical Constituents of Essential Oil from Anethum Sowa Kurz. *Seed Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2012; 4(9): 4156-4160.
34. Saleh-E-In MM, Sultana N, Rahim MM, Ahsan MA, Bhuiyan MN, Hossain MN, Rahman MM, Kumar Roy S, Islam MR. Chemical composition and pharmacological significance of Anethum Sowa L. Root. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2017 Feb 23; 17(1): 127. doi: 10.1186/s12906-017-1601-y. PMID: 28231789; PMCID: PMC5324201.
35. Dr. Manisha Kumari Kharadi Dr. Vipin Kumar Yadav Dr. Ashwini Kumar Sharma and Dr. Rajesh Chandra Mishra on A review on traditional uses and thereputic indications of anethum sowa. *Volume.*, 8(9): 239-248.
36. Wasim Akram, S., Arokiarajan, M., Christopher, J. et al. Antimicrobial and antioxidant study of combined essential oils of Anethum Sowa Kurz. and *Trachyspermum ammi* (L.) along with quality determination, comparative histo-anatomical features, GC–MS and HPTLC chemometrics. *Sci. Rep.*, 2024; 14: 27010. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-75773-8>.
37. Harborne JB. *Phytochemical Methods: A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis*. 3rd ed. Springer; 1998.
38. Shahidi F, Ambigaipalan P. Phenolics and polyphenolics in foods, beverages and spices: Antioxidant activity and health effects. *J Funct Foods.* 2015; 18: 820-897.